

Affectation and Make-Belief World in Manohar Malgonkar's *Upper Division Love*

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Abstract

The aim of the paper is to create awareness in the mind of young men and young women. They must keep aesthetic distance from the celluloid world. Watching Test matches is a time consuming activity. Watching film is a time consuming activity. Adoring any heroine is a foolish act. It is the duty of any fan to appreciate the attitude of the heroine as well as the hero. They have no right to cross the limits. Film world has a long history. The attitude of the layman is not at all changed. They have an infatuation with any actresses. They fail to discern the artificiality of the celluloid world. Manohar Malgonkar has depicted the activities of the lower division clerk in a very shrewd manner. This issue has a contemporary relevance. It is an everlasting issue it touches the raw nerve of the readers. The lower division clerk behaves in a very childish manner. He has no maturity and responsibility. His life is a fruitful lesson to all young men and young women. Imaginary world or 'Make Belief' world is a key issue. "a delicate skirting of the common life of India."

So the writer has scrutinized this burning issue in a detailed manner. The protagonist of this story does not learn any useful lesson from his bitter experiences. He has undergone untold suffering in the hands of Ramakant and Sunderbala. He finds it very difficult to alter his attitude. He cannot help adoring another actress named Shilamati. The indirect message of the story is "old habit dies hard".

Keywords: infatuation, affectation, aantasy, mock love, artificiality, hollowness, childish.

Manohar Malgonkar is one of the most remarkable novelists and short story writers of modern times. He has brought to his writings, his rich experience of academic life and princely India. His Significant works are A Bend in the Ganges, Distant Drum, Beware Bombay, A Sky in Amber and Combat of Shadows. Upper Division Love is the Story of a small clerk's infatuation with a popular film star and his subsequent disillusionment through envy and humiliation.

Manohar Malgonkar has a sense of social responsibility. He delineates the character very acutely. The aim of this paper is to point out the difference between genuine love and mock love. Real world is entirely different from celluloid world. Most of the young men and young women spoil their life in the form of watching television and watching movies. Watching movie is a time consuming activity. Common people fail to keep aesthetic distance from the celluloid world. They reckon 'imagination' as 'real' and 'real' as imagination.

In this story '*Upper Division Love*' the name of the protagonist is not at all mentioned. Manohar Malgonkar deliberately avoids mentioning the name of the protagonist. The lower division clerk is not at all responsible. He happens to get chicken feed salary. He never thinks about self development and the welfare of his family. He is travelling in the 'Imaginary World'. The lower division clerk fails to do his duty very earnestly. He behaves like a malingerer. Manohar Malgonkar has pointed out the stark realism in his work very sharply. He describes the activities of the lower division clerk in a very clever manner. He describes the behavior of the clerk in the form of hard boiled realism. He said

There were three photographs of her in my room and one in my wallet. I had seen every picture in which She had acted I knew all her songs to the slightest meaningful pause, and once I was so carried away by an enormous poster of her in front of the Bolero Theatre, that I gave up my place in the bus queue to be able to gaze at it longer. (*Upper Division Love*, p1)

The lower division clerk is a cinema buff. He always thinks about his favorite film star Sunderbala. He considers Sunderbala as 'heart-throb'. He feels dumbfounded while looking at her photograph. He has moved heaven and earth in the form of collecting photographs. He is very eager to see all her pictures. He behaves like a movie friend. He tends to forget his duties. He has strained every nerve to memorise her songs. He wallows in the world of imagination. He behaves like a drunkard. Drunkard has the habit of forgetting the real world. Like that the lower division clerk forgets his duty as well as his responsibility. The duty of office goes is to nurture his family. The responsibility of office goes is to maintain the financial condition very properly. He must have filial responsibility. He must think about his work always. But the lower division clerk forgets his entire responsibility.

The paper has a contemporary relevance. Watching movie and mega serial is a time consuming activity. The lower division clerk behaves like a typical Indian. One should watch movie only for entertainment purpose. One should keep aesthetic distance from the celluloid world. Young girls and young boys are like screenagers. They spend a considerable amount of time in the form of watching movies. Film world is a fantasy world. It is very difficult to find stark realism in the film world. Film world is not at all real world. It is a sort of make-belief world. In the recent newspaper article one can come across the shocking news of a person's activity. A son thoughtlessly killed his father. His father has refused to provide him money for watching the movie. It is rather the shocking news. Manohar Malgonkar wrote this story like a seer. He has analyzed the recent trends very acutely. He feels panic stricken to watch the activities of lower middle class people. Lower middle class people polluted themselves in the form of watching movies. The situation is not at all changed today. He has depicted the recent trends of any youngster in a fairly clever manner. Most of the people live in 'Make-Belief' world or 'Imaginary world' for a long time. There is no scope for self improvement and intellectual pursuit. The purpose behind writing this paper is to create awareness in the minds of the young girls as well as young boys. They should have some social responsibility. They should have some civic sense. They must think about the welfare of their family. They should behave like good citizens as: "Oh thank you" She said and her eyebrows arched, her nose crinkled, her eyes lit up, and Her teeth flashed. For a moment, the famous smile was turned on just for me.

Then it was turned off, abruptly as though it were all controlled by a switch" (*Upper Division Love*, p2).

In this story, Sunderbala is the favorite film star. She is in her "hey-days" She makes all the youngsters sleepless. Her smile, love and concern are not real. There is a vast difference between affection and affectation. Affection is real. Affectation is not real. There is a vast difference between genuine love and mock love. Sunderbala smiled at the lower division clerk. It reveals her

affection. It is not at affection. Mother's selfless love is affection. Brother's concern is affection. Wife's fret reveals her affection indirectly. But the smile of the heroine is not at all a replica of affection. The lower division clerk fails to discern this. He becomes the victim of "Make Belief" world or "Imaginary world". The lower division clerk and Sunderbala shackled up together only in the imaginary world. Without having any decency, he goes on describing her teeth, her eyes, her nose, her smile etc. The smile of Sunderbala is quite artificial. It is not quite artificial. It is not at all real. It reveals her acting and mock love. The lower division clerk has the prospect of sitting with her cheek by jowl only in the imaginary world. He never thinks about his self development. Sunderbala can a mass wealth in the form of smiling, gazing, mock loving etc. She has the capacity to convert all her gesticulations into money. But the lower division clerk is a fool. He has no commonsense to realize either the 'Make Belief' world or affectation. In this story, Manohar Malgonkar has introduced one another character. His name is Ramakant. He has the capacity to do all the incredible things or action in the form the stunt sequence of Ramakant makes the audience guffaw. They may make acerbic comments about his stunt sequence. The action sequence is not real one can apply the theory of S.T. Coleridge while watching any film. ST Coleridge, the prominent poet of the romantic period has advocated the theory named "Willing suspension of Disbelief Theory". All the heroes of celluloid world have to think about this particular theory. The film world is an imaginary world. They happen to project all incredible things in the film. It does not happen in the real world. But the lower division clerk has no such commonsense to apply this theory named "Willing Suspense of disbelief Theory". Ramakant has the privilege to make either 'mock love' or 'genuine love' to any heroines. He can play with the emotions of the heroines. He can apply any dirty tricks to seduce any heroines. Sunderbala has an emotional attachment with Ramakant. Sunderbala is a real hypersensitive heroine in the story "*Upper Division Love*", she feels intemperate very often. She relishes the bill and cooing of Ramakant. She does not feel repulsive towards the touch of Ramakant. She smiled at Ramakant for time being. She can sever ties with Ramakant under any circumstances. Even her emotional attachment of Sunderbala does not have an everlasting value. It discloses her affectation but not affection. There is no scope for permanent relationship in the celluloid world. There is no scope for platonic love in the film world. The film world is either 'Make Belief' or the world of 'affection'. The lower division clerk does not go to office regularly. He is behaving like the truant. He behaves like thick skinned fellow. He applies for 'French leave' very often. He is a real malingerer in that office. He shirks from responsibility. But he can pick holes in the attitude of superintendent. Manohar Malgonkar in the story 'Lower Division Love' has described the attitude of lower division clerk very beautifully. "From the studio I rang up my office and told the superintendent. That I had fever and a bad pain in the stomach, and the Doctor had advised me ten day's rest" (*Upper Division Love*, p4).

The behavior of the lower division clerk is childish. He behaves like a dull student. He is very dull in completing his work. He does his work in a very slipshod manner. He is a movie friend. At the same time he wastes his time brutally in the form of watching test matches. He has no productive time. He wastes his time callously. He has no awareness about the proverb "Time is Gold" or "A stitch in time saves none". He has avoided his responsibility deliberately. He cannot do his clerical work out of passion. He does his work very indifferently. He has an undue passion towards the film actress Sunderbala. He has spoilt his life altogether for her sake. He is a thick-skinned fellow. He is not at all responsible. Most of the office goers think about the prospect of promotion. They want to leapfrog their position. They never give room for laziness. They are always duty conscious. The lower division clerk is basically a lumpen. He is the spoilt child. He thinks about the film world. He thinks about test matches. He never thinks about his promotion. He never thinks about getting higher perks. Watching movies is not at all his habit. It is his weakness. He gives undue attachment

towards the film world. He finds it very difficult to avoid both things namely watching test matches or admiring actress. He comes across a series of dramatic events. It leads the 'lower division' clerks to the realization not only of the utter futility of his passion, but also the artificiality and hollowness of the "upper division" film world. This does not deter him. He never changes his attitude even at the end of the story. He is the perfect example to prove the famous proverb "Old habit dies hard". Manohar Malgonkar has made the sarcastic remarks on lower division clerk. He describes: "I have only just discovered that she (Shilamati) works in the Ajaib film company which has its studio behind the Botanical Gardens, right on my way to the office" (*Upper Division Love* p14)

In the beginning, the lower division clerk gazed at Sunderbala, a film star. In the end, he gazed at Shilamati another film star. So he cannot help adoring one actress or the other. He finds it very difficult to change his nature. There are more than millions of people living like him. He is a real specimen in the million. This issue has a universal appeal. This issue is everlasting. Even today one can see a lot of youngsters are powering several liters of milk on the banner. They prostrate themselves in front of their favorite actor. This activity still sustains in this contemporary world. Manohar Malgonkar has an astute sense to scrutinize the recent or common attitude of the people through the character of Sunderbala, Ramakant and the lower division clerk. M.K.Naik observes "even when he deals with situations of strong social import in stories like *Bondage* and 'Two Red Roosters, Malgorikar seems to be more interested in the surprise ending than in the social problems involved.

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